

Oxalyldihydrazide as a New Absorbing Reagent for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Sulphur Dioxide

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Several methods of determination of sulphur dioxide in ambient air have been reported in the literature¹. Most of the spectrophotometric methods are based on collection of ambient sulphur dioxide in a suitable absorbing medium²⁻⁴ for subsequent determination using different reagents such as P-AAB and PRA etc. Some reagents containing amino and similar groups^{5,6} have also been used as an absorbing medium for sulphur dioxide.

In the proposed method oxalyldihydrazide (ODH) (CONHNH₂) has been used as an efficient absorbing agent for sulphur dioxide and found to be suitable due to its high solubility in water and greater stability of sulphur dioxide in it, without any rigid control of pH, temperature and concentration of the absorbing agent. The absorbed sulphur dioxide is then estimated spectrophotometrically using either *p*-aminoazobenzene (P-AAB) or pararosaniline (PRA) in presence of formaldehyde.

Results and Discussion

The λ_{\max} value for P-AAB is 505 nm and that for PRA 545 nm. Reagent blank also absorbs in the respective regions though with low intensity. The actual absorbance was calculated as reported in literature⁷. The proposed reagent has 99-100% absorption efficiency. The second impingers gave no test for sulphur dioxide. Sulphur dioxide trapped in ODH was found stable for one week.

The order of addition of reagents is important. To the absorbed sulphur dioxide in ODH, P-AAB or PRA was added first followed by addition of formaldehyde and HCl for maximum colour development. When formaldehyde was added prior to the addition of P-AAB or PRA to the sulphur dioxide solution, no colour development was observed.

After adding P-AAB to sulphur dioxide solution, the acidity was adjusted to ~0.02 M (HCl). Then formaldehyde (1 ml) and 2 M HCl (1 ml) were added to it and the volume was made upto 25 ml with distilled water. The dye-acid concentration used in case of PRA was 0.02% dye (2 ml) and 6% conc. HCl (2 ml) maintaining pH ~1.2. In the earlier reported method⁷ the product was stable for 1 h or less. In the present method, full colour development took 20 min, and the coloured product was stable for ~6 h.

For P-AAB and PRA the coloured products obeyed Beer's law in the ranges 0.12-1.2 and 0.08-1.0 ppm of sulphur dioxide respectively, trapped in both the cases in 0.1 M ODH solution.

Nitrogen dioxide is the main interferant. The use of malonyl dihydrazide has been reported for the elimination of its interference⁸. In the proposed method, ODH which is used as an absorbing medium, itself eliminates the interference of upto 20 ppm nitrogen dioxide. The removal of hydrogen sulphide from air was done by passing it through lead acetate solution. The effects of Fe^{III} and Mn^{II} which are known to catalyse the oxidation of sulphur dioxide was studied by adding known amount of each ion to sulphur dioxide solution. No significant interference was observed by the presence of Fe^{III} and Mn^{II} which normally catalyse the oxidation of the absorbed sulphur dioxide.

The present method was applied to the determination of sulphur dioxide in various samples of air. The amount of sulphur dioxide was then determined by the present method and also by the reported method⁴; the results were found to be in good agreement. The present method avoids the use of hazardous mercury(II) salts and is as sensitive as the method of West and Gaeke². Oxalyldihydrazide was found to be very effective as an absorbent for sulphur dioxide since nitrogen dioxide, the common interferant in other methods does not interfere upto 200 ppm (Table 1). For higher quantity of nitrogen dioxide (>20 ppm), 2 ml of 0.6% sulphuric acid is to be added to the absorbing solution prior to sampling.

TABLE I—COMPARISON WITH OTHER SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHODS

Sl. no.	Absorbing solution	Chromogen	Range of determination $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Remarks
1.	Tetrachloro mercurate ^a	PRA	0-1.4	Use of hazardous Hg ^{II} salts
2.	Monoethanol amine ^b	P-AAB	0.8-8.0	Less sensitive
3.	Hydroxamic acids ^c	P-AAB	0.1-1.0	Nitrogen dioxide is main interferant
4.	Semicarbazide ^d	P-AAB	0.1-1.0	Nitrogen dioxide does not interfere upto 8 ppm
5.	Present method	PRA P-AAB	0.08-1.0 0.12-1.2	Sensitive, the interference of 20 ppm nitrogen dioxide is eliminated by the absorbing medium itself

^aRef. 6. ^bRef. 10. ^cRef. 8. ^dRef. 12.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. A Carl-Zeiss

Spekol spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched silica cells was used. Fritted midget impingers of 35 ml capacity were used for air sampling. PIMCO calibrated rotameters was used for adjusting the flow rate.

A 0.02% aqueous solution of recrystallised *p*-aminoazobenzene (P-AAB) (Sisco) and a 0.02% aqueous solution of pararosanine (PRA) (Sigma) were used. A 0.1 M solution of oxalyldihydrazide was prepared in demineralised water. The reagent was prepared and purified by the reported method⁹

Sulphur dioxide : Since the standard samples of sulphur dioxide were not available, it was generated from freshly prepared and standardised sodium sulphite to which HCl was added dropwise as reported earlier for calibration purposes^{5,6}. To known amount of freshly prepared sulphite (2–30 µg) solution, 0.5 M HCl (2 ml) was added to liberate sulphur dioxide which was absorbed in the absorbing reagent using air sampling train and analysed

Procedure : Air containing various concentrations of sulphur dioxide was passed through absorbing solution (10 ml) taken in two midget impingers connected in series at a rate of 0.75 dm³ min⁻¹ for 30 min. The absorbing solution was then mixed with P-AAB or PRA (1 ml) and the acidity was adjusted with 2 M HCl (1 ml) in case of P-AAB, and

the dye-acid concentration in case of PRA was 2 ml of 0.02% and 2 ml of 6% conc. HCl respectively, to maintain pH ~1.2. Then formaldehyde (1 ml) and 2 M HCl (1 ml) were added to it, the volume was made upto 25 ml with distilled water and the colour measured at 505 nm for P-AAB and 545 nm for PRA

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